

THE CONCEPT OF THE LIABILITY OF IN INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW

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Abstract: The human mind is endowed with more potential than we can imagine and harness in a single human lifetime. In addition, the human brain is able to withstand any load of the processes of learning, memorization and creativity and could handle even a billion times more. The proof of these words is intellectual activity. Intellectual property is a relatively new and constantly evolving institution of civil law, plays a vital role and covers a wide range of areas of intellectual activity of society.

The relevance of the topic under study lies in the fact that the product of human intellectual activity requires reliable protection by the state and compliance with the law by society.

“In the most general form,” notes G.V. Atamanchuk, - responsibility represents the attitude, ensuring the interests and support of independent parties, as well as guaranteed society and support. It arose on the basis of the continuous interaction of three components: a) consciousness of duty; b) evaluate behavior, c) impose sanctions. [1]

One of the problematic aspects is that legal responsibility is often mistakenly identified with other, related categories. Legal liability establishes the consequences of inappropriate (illegal) behavior that violates the rights and interests of other persons. Consequently, its use becomes one of the ways to protect violated rights and interests. The most important feature of this method is the application of liability measures with the help of state, including judicial coercion, that is, with the help of public authority (authorized state bodies or officials). This distinguishes it from self-defense and other measures of influence applied to offenders directly by authorized (victim) persons. In some cases, penalties can be used voluntarily, and not with the help of public authority (for example, the offender voluntarily pays a fine). This circumstance does not change their nature as state-coercive measures, the content and procedure for application of which are established by law. Therefore, legal liability is often considered as state-compulsory application of any unfavorable measures to the offender.

Legal liability is one of the forms of state coercive influence on violators of the law, which consists in applying to them sanctions provided for by law - measures of responsibility that entail additional adverse consequences for them.

At this time, liability for violations of intellectual property rights is established by the norms of articles 1070, 1090, 1096, 1107, 1111 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, part 4 of articles 155, 177, 177¹, 177² CoAO of the Republic of Uzbekistan, art. 149 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [2]

At the moment, a large number of scientific studies reveal a comprehensive study of the legal protection and protection of intellectual rights. These scientific studies are aimed at studying civil liability in the field of intellectual property, while, according to some scientists, there is a need to consider liability for offenses in the field of intellectual property as an interdisciplinary institution of law, as this contributes to a more detailed study of its mechanism. Intellectual rights are protected within the framework of protective legal relations that restore the violated legal order in the field of intellectual property, as a result of which measures of civil, administrative or criminal liability are applied.

As we know, the copyright holder or author of intellectual property objects owns exclusive

rights, which are secured by legal acts. Violation of the exclusive rights of the author or copyright holder leads to liability.

However, the most common violations are violations of copyright and rights to personalization. In the field of copyright and related rights, the most common use of works without the permission of the author. The main reason for such a widespread violation of these rights is characterized by the economic aspect: the price of intellectual property may be excessively high in relation to the material capabilities or expectations of users of the works. This situation can lead to the spread of counterfeit goods. In addition, the Internet is considered one of the ideal places for rights violations, which allows you to use copyrighted works freely and completely free of charge.

In the area of rights to means of individualization, the most popular violation can be called plagiarism. Plagiarism is the deliberate appropriation of an idea, invention, work of science or art belonging to another person. For example, an organization appropriates a trademark that differs slightly from the trademark of another enterprise. Such actions are aimed at deceiving buyers, as a result of which the company that originally owned the trademark may suffer losses. The transformation to the information age of social development was determined by a significant increase in the volume of investments in the creation of results of intellectual activity. The creation of intellectual property is an essential tool for achieving success in the economic sphere. In many cases, profit is derived not from the intellectual property itself, but from concluding agreements with third parties for use for a fee. For example, licensing agreements for the right to use intellectual property: works of science, literature, art; trademarks and service marks, industrial designs and other results of intellectual activity provided for in Article 1031 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The rapid development of this type of social relations gives rise to the need to reform legislation.

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